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Cyber Security Practices And Fraud Prevention Of Deposit Money Banks In Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the cyber security practices and fraud prevention of deposit money banks in Anambra state. The researcher developed three specific objectives which were to: Assess the effect of network security system, transaction monitoring system, and multi-factor authentication on fraud prevention of deposit money banks in Anambra state. This study is anchored on Protection Motivation Theory (PMT). Data were generated through primary sources. The method for data collection was the questionnaire which was administered randomly among the staff of the deposit money bank in Nigeria. The population of the study was four thousand six hundred and twenty-nine (4,629). The sample size of the study was eight hundred and ninety (890) through Borg & Gall (1973) formular. eight hundred and seventy-three (873) copies of questionnaire were retrieved. The hypotheses were tested using multiple regression analysis method at 0.05% level of significance. Findings from the study revealed that; network security system (NSS) had significant effect on Fraud prevention of deposit money bank in Anambra state. (t-test 2.051, $p=0.002$); transaction monitoring system cost had significant effect on Fraud prevention of deposit money bank in Anambra state (t-test 2.014, $p=0.003$). Multi-factor authentication had significant effect on Fraud prevention of deposit money bank in in Anambra state (t-test 2.112, $p=0.001$). The study recommended that banks should continue to invest in advanced network security infrastructure such as firewalls, intrusion detection and prevention systems, secure VPNs, and updated antivirus software. Banks should implement more sophisticated real-time transaction monitoring tools that use artificial intelligence and data analytics to detect unusual or suspicious activities. Banks should require multi-factor authentication for all customer and staff access to banking systems.

Keywords: network security system, transaction monitoring system, and multi-factor authentication, cyber security practices, fraud prevention, deposit money banks

1.1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the rapid growth of information communication technology has profoundly transformed the banking industry, shaping how financial transactions are conducted and how services are delivered. This transformation has led to increased adoption of digital banking channels such as internet banking, mobile banking, automated teller machines (ATMs), electronic funds transfers, and online payment platforms (Austin-Olowo, Anike,. and Ailemen, 2023),. While these technological advancements have enhanced operational efficiency and customer convenience, they have also exposed deposit money banks to a wide range of cybersecurity threats and fraudulent activities. Cybersecurity refers to the combination of technologies, policies, practices, and controls designed to protect systems, networks, devices, and data from unauthorized access, attacks, damage, or theft. In the context of banking, cybersecurity (Chitimira,

and Ncube, 2021), practices are critical for safeguarding sensitive financial information, maintaining the integrity of transactions, and preserving customer trust. As banks increasingly rely on digital platforms to process and store financial data, the vulnerability to cyberattacks such as hacking, malware attacks, phishing, denial-of-service (DoS) attacks, and identity theft has grown significantly (Natile. & Sheila 2025). These threats pose serious risks not only to the profitability and reputation of financial institutions but also to the stability of the financial system as a whole.

In tandem with cybersecurity concerns, fraud continues to be a significant challenge for deposit money banks in Nigeria (Dlamini, and Mbambo, 2019). Fraud in banking can take various forms, including ATM fraud, card cloning, insider fraud, unauthorized access to accounts, and sophisticated online scams. The prevalence of such fraudulent activities undermines customer confidence, increases operational costs, and can lead to substantial financial losses (Ghelani, 2022). Consequently, effective fraud prevention measures are essential to detect, deter, and mitigate fraudulent activities within banking operations. In Anambra State, a region characterized by vibrant commercial activity and increasing demand for financial services, deposit money banks play a pivotal role in economic development by mobilizing savings, facilitating payments, and extending credit. However, as these banks continue to embrace digital banking solutions, the challenges associated with cybersecurity and fraud have become more pronounced (Natile & Sheila 2025). This has necessitated the adoption of robust cybersecurity frameworks and proactive fraud prevention strategies to protect both the banks and their customers. Understanding the interrelationship between cybersecurity practices and fraud prevention is essential for enhancing the operational resilience and performance of deposit money banks in Anambra State. This study seeks to explore the range of cybersecurity measures implemented by banks, evaluate the effectiveness of fraud prevention strategies, and assess the extent to which these practices contribute to reducing financial losses and enhancing customer confidence.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine the cyber security practices and fraud prevention of deposit money banks in Anambra state The specific objectives are to:

1. Assess the effect of network security system on fraud prevention of deposit money banks in Anambra state
2. Determine the effect of transaction monitoring system on fraud prevention of deposit money banks in Anambra state
3. Investigate the effect of multi-factor authentication on fraud prevention of deposit money banks in Anambra state

Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Cybersecurity

Cybersecurity refers to the comprehensive framework of technologies, processes, policies, controls, and human practices designed to protect computer systems, digital networks, devices, and data from unauthorized access, cyberattacks, disruption, damage, or theft. It is a critical discipline within information technology that focuses on safeguarding digital assets and ensuring the secure operation of interconnected systems in an increasingly digital world (Malik, Noreen, & Awan, 2018).. Cybersecurity goes beyond simply installing antivirus software or firewalls; it represents a holistic and strategic approach to managing digital risks. It encompasses multiple layers of protection across hardware, software, networks, and human users (Natile. & Sheila 2025). These layers work together to create a secure digital environment capable of resisting and responding to evolving cyber threats. cybersecurity can be defined as the multidimensional system of technological safeguards, organizational policies, human practices, and risk management strategies designed to protect digital systems, networks, and information from cyber threats, ensuring confidentiality, integrity, availability, and operational continuity in a digitally connected environment (Ojeka, Ben-Caleb. & EKpe, 2017)..

2.1.2 Fraud Prevention

Fraud prevention refers to the comprehensive and proactive system of policies, internal controls, technological safeguards, monitoring mechanisms, and ethical standards designed to deter, detect, and minimize fraudulent activities within an organization or institution (Kimani, Oduol, and Langat, 2019). It is a structured approach aimed at reducing opportunities for fraud, identifying suspicious behavior at an early stage, and ensuring swift corrective action to prevent financial loss, reputational damage, and operational disruption. Fraud itself involves intentional deception, misrepresentation, concealment, or abuse of trust for personal or financial gain. It may occur in various forms such as embezzlement, identity theft, financial statement manipulation, cyber fraud, insider abuse, asset misappropriation, and electronic payment scams (Li, & Liu, 2021). Fraud prevention, therefore, is not limited to responding to fraud after it has occurred; rather, it focuses primarily on creating systems that make fraudulent activities difficult to commit and easy to detect. Fraud prevention is not merely an operational function but a strategic responsibility that requires management commitment and organizational support (Bharti, Himanshu, & Sonika 2025). It contributes to financial stability, enhances stakeholder confidence, improves regulatory compliance, and protects organizational reputation. In sectors such as banking—where large volumes of financial transactions occur daily fraud prevention is essential to safeguarding customer funds and maintaining trust in the financial system (Ohanyere, Arinze, & Atueyi 2025). fraud prevention can be defined as a coordinated and proactive organizational framework consisting of internal controls, risk management strategies, technological safeguards, ethical standards, monitoring systems, and governance mechanisms designed to deter, detect, and minimize fraudulent activities, thereby protecting financial resources, ensuring operational integrity, and sustaining public confidence.

2.2 Theoretical Review

Protection Motivation Theory (PMT) PMT explains how perceived threats motivate protective behavior through two appraisals: threat appraisal (severity and vulnerability) and coping appraisal (response efficacy, self efficacy, and cost). In Nigerian Deposit Money Banks, rising incidents heighten perceived risk and trigger actions such as larger cybersecurity budgets, real time detection and response investments, structured self assessments, and routine vulnerability and penetration testing. These choices aim to reduce losses, shorten detection and response time, and preserve customer trust and Return on Equity. PMT also clarifies why boards fund staff awareness, simulations, and clear incident playbooks: they raise risk salience and confidence in the bank's ability to respond. In short, PMT frames cybersecurity as a motivated, evidence based response to perceived danger, converting risk perception into concrete controls and measurable performance gains.

2.3 Empirical Review

Ohanyere, Arinze and Atueyi (2025) investigated the digital cyberspace cost on firm performance of deposit money bank using data for the period of 2012-2023. The objectives of this study were to: determine the extent to which cyber security maintenance cost affects on firm performance of deposit money bank in Nigeria; evaluate the extent to which cyber security acquisition cost affects on performance of deposit money bank in Nigeria. Panel least squared (PLS) method of data analysis was adopted because of its Best Linear Unbiased Estimators (BLUE) properties. The data for the variables used was sourced from annual report of the selected deposit money bank in Nigeria. The variables were on cyber security maintenance cost and cyber security acquisition cost. The study adopted the descriptive statistics, correlation approach, as well as panel least square. E- View software was used for the analysis. The study found that Cyber security maintenance cost has significant effect on performance of deposit money bank in Nigeria. (t-test 3.491757, p=0.0008). Cyber security acquisition cost has no significant effect on performance of deposit money bank in Nigeria. (t-test 0.959399, p=0.3405).

Bharti, Himanshu, and Sonika (2025) examined the effect of cyber-security actions on the banking industry's supply chain in its ability to recover, sustain and manage risk. This work used a questionnaire that targeted managers and clients and involved 30 managers and 260 digital banking clients. Out of the data collected, 200 were legitimate for analysis using PLS-SEM V4 and IBM SPSS V26. In our survey, we also discarded 30 responses as they did not provide valid responses to the survey including having a

standard deviation of zero and identified as outliers using Cook's distance. The research explored current approaches in risk mitigation through a variety of mechanisms such as zero-trust architecture, incident response frameworks, and vendor risk assessments. The results showed that well-established, knowledgeable managers were aware of and taking cyber-security actions. This makes it clear that stakeholders need to regularly evaluate cyber security practice training and talks. However, clients providing banks a passing mark to collaboratively educate clients regarding cyber-security risks better given they were satisfied with the level of security in their accounts.

Natile and Sheila (2025) identified cyber security threats that hinder the adoption of digital banking and provide sustainable strategies to combat cyber security risks in the banking industry. Systematic literature review guidelines were used to conduct a quantitative synthesis of empirical evidence regarding the impact of cyber security threats and risks on the adoption of digital banking. A total of 84 studies were initially examined, and after applying the selection and eligibility criteria for this systematic review, 58 studies were included. These selected articles consistently identified identity theft, malware attacks, phishing and vishing as significant cyber security threats that hinder the adoption of digital banking. With the country's banking sector being new in this area, this study contributes to the scant literature on cyber security, which is mostly in need due to the myriad breaches that the industry has already suffered thus far.

Ama, Onwubiko and Nwankwo, (2024) investigated cyber security challenges in Nigerian deposit money banks (DMBs) with a focus on proactive measures taken by banks and customers to overcome these challenges. The research design employs a descriptive approach and census sampling, with data collected from staff of selected DMBs using questionnaires. Data analysis was conducted using SPSS, and findings indicate that the major challenges confronting cyber security in banks were pharming, identity theft, SIM Swap fraud, Skimming/Website cloning and Smishing/Vishing. The major factors responsible were found to include loopholes in the banks' internal control system, insider abuse by bank staff, ignorance and lack of security consciousness among the banking customers etc. it was found that banks implement measures such as encryption, password changes, and blocking unsolicited messages to mitigate cyber security risks. Dalia, Tariq and Eman (2024) examined the impact of cyber security disclosure on banks' performance and (2) explore whether the existence of a chief risk officer (CRO), an information technology (IT) committee, and a board of directors (BOD)' size moderates the association between cyber security disclosure and bank performance. The study used manual textual analysis to measure cyber security disclosure in a sample of listed banks in the MENA region countries based on data from 2019 to 2021. The data were collected from annual reports and financial statements of banks available at Orbis Bank Focus database. The study employed a random effect regression model to test the hypotheses and discuss the results. The findings show that banks in the MENA region are increasingly interested in disclosing cyber security information, where cyber security disclosure over the sample years is increasing from 17% in 2019 to 19.6% in 2021. In addition, the results show that cyber security disclosure has a positive and significant influence on bank performance. Furthermore, the findings indicate that the presence of a CRO moderates the relationship between cyber security disclosure and bank performance. These findings show that depending largely on a bank's CRO to handle complex and dynamic risks can have serious consequences for decision making processes connected to managing cyber security risk and disclosure.

METHODOLOGY

3.1: Research Design

The research design that was adopted in this study is the descriptive survey strategy, it was used in this study to seek clarifications and convenience on the part of the respondent given schedules.

3.2: Sources of Data

The primary source of data is the sampling or study unit regarding in (or form) which information is collected on first hand basis. The researcher did not adopt any rigid method in the collection of data; rather data was collected as the problem demanded creativity and judgment also played a vital role at this

stage of the project, knowing that the final judgment will be partly constrained by the type and value of the information collected.

3.3: Population of the Study.

This describes number of staff in selected deposit money bank in, Anambra, which constitutes the universe of this study. The population of interest therefore consisted of all workers in deposit money banks in Anambra State. However six commercial banks with international authorization operating in the state were selected for the study by the use of purposive sampling. Thus, the study population for this research comprises of employees of the selected commercial banks in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Table 3.1 Selected Banks

s/n	Bank	Population	Nnewi	Onitsha	Awka	Total
1	Fidelity bank	423	3	10	3	16
2	First bank	765	2	11	6	19
3	Access bank	1,332	3	12	5	20
4	Union bank	514	1	3	2	6
5	GT bank	823	1	4	2	7
6	UBA	772	3	10	6	19
	Total	4,629				

Sources: Researcher’s Compilation, 2026

3.4: Determination of Sample Size

The sample size for this study will be determined by using the Borg & Gall formular of (1973). Statistically, the Borg & Gall (1973) formular for sample size is given by

$$n = (Zx)^2(e) [N]$$

$$(Zx)^2 = 1.960$$

e = Error margin (0.05)

N = Population of Interest =

X = Significance Level

3.5 Sample size determination

Given the nature of this study, it was difficult to cover the entire population of (4629), so a fair representative sample of the population therefore was imperative. Accordingly, the sample size for the study was determined by using the Borg & Gall (1973) formular for calculating sample size as follows

$$n = (1.960)^2 (0.05) [4629]$$

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$$n = (3.8461) (231.45)$$

$$= 890.171945 \implies 890$$

$$n = 890$$

3.6: Method of Data Analysis.

Statistics such as frequency count and percentages were put to use in the analysis of research questions while research hypotheses were tested using regression method analysis. The research hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Analysis was carried out with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.

DATA ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION

In this section, the data generated from the staff of the sampled firms were presented, analyzed and interpreted. Eight hundred and Ninety (890) questionnaire were administered, However, eight hundred and thirty-seven (837) questionnaire were retrieved 93.2% was the percentage rate of returned questionnaire. Therefore the analysis and interpretation of data were based on the returned questionnaires. The method used was the percentage tables. And ANOVA regression was used for the hypothesis testing. The first section covers the demographic features of the respondents. The second section analyzed the data relevant and hypotheses

4.1 Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

In this section, the demographic features of the respondents such as gender, marital status, age bracket, educational qualification and working experience are presented and analyzed. A total of eight hundred and ninety respondents were sampled and the results are presented in the table below.

Table 4.1.1: Gender of the Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	387	49.1	46.2	46.2
	Female	486	51.9	53.8	53.8
	Total	873	98.9	100.0	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2026/SPSS, Version 23

The above table reveals that the 46.2% of the respondents which represents three hundred and eighty-seven (387) persons were male respondents, while four hundred and eighty-six (486) respondents which represent 53.8% were female respondents. By implication, female respondents were more than male respondents by 7.6% in our selected population for this study. The implication of this is to enable us to know the number of female and male that successfully returned their questionnaire.

Table 4.1.2: Marital Status of the Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Single	380	40	43.5	40
	Married	486	58	55.6	58
	Others	7	2	1	1
	Total	873	100	100.0	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2026/SPSS, Version 23

In the table above, out of the three hundred and eighty (380) respondents, representing 43.5% are single while four hundred and eighty (480) respondents which represent 55.6 percent are married. While seven respondents (7) which represents 1% were among widowed, divorced and separated. This was because these married are 486 represents 58% more than single 380 representing 40%.

Table 4.1.3: Age Bracket of the Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18 - 30 years	330	35	35	48.6
	31 - 40 years	220	24	24	74.0
	41 - 50 years	198	21.1	21.1	89.7
	51 years and above	125	20.1	20.1	100.0
	Total	873	98.9	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2026/SPSS, Version 23

Table 4.3 above depicted the age bracket of the respondents. The distribution shows that 35% of the respondents are between the age brackets of 18 to 30 years while 220 respondents representing 24% are within the age bracket of 31 - 40 years. On the same note, 21.1% of the respondents are within the age bracket of 41 - 50 years while the remaining respondents representing 20.1% are within the age bracket of 51 years and above.

4.2 Multiple Regression Analysis

Multiple regression result was employed to test the effect of independent or explanatory variables on the dependent variable. The result of the multiple regression analysis is presented in the tables below.

Table 4.2.1 Summary of the Regression Result

The result of the multiple regressions is presented in the tables below.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				Durbin-Watson	
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2		Sig. F Change
1	.721 ^a	.520	.516	.48642	.520	134.559	3	870	.000	1.542

a. Predictors: (Constant), NSS, TMS, MFA

b. Dependent Variable: FDP

Table 3 shows that R² which measures the strength of the effect of independent variable on the dependent variable has the value of 52%. This implies that 52% of the variation in fraud prevention (FDP) is explained by variations in network security system (NSS), transaction monitoring system (TMS) and multi-factor authentication (MFA). This was supported by adjusted R² of 51.6%. Decision rule for Durbin Watson say that when the Durbin Watson d-statistics is 2 or close to 2, there is no autocorrelation in the model otherwise there is. In our model Durbin-Watson statistics of 1.542 approx 2 in table above shows that the variables in the model are not autocorrelated and that the model is reliable for predications.

Table 4.2.2: ANOVA Result

ANOVAa

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	95.512	3	31.837	134.559	.000 ^b
	Residual	88.254	870	.237		
	Total	183.767	873			

a. Dependent Variable: FDP

b. Predictors: (Constant), NSS, TMS, MFA

The f-statistics value of 134.559 in table 4.2.2 with f-statistics probability of 0.000 shows that the independent variables has significant effect on dependent. This shows, the network security system (NSS), Transaction monitoring system (TMS) and multi-factor authentication (MFA), can collectively explain the variations in fraud prevention of deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Table 4.2.3 Coefficients of the Model

T-statistics and probability value from the regression result are the effect of individual independent or explanatory variables on the dependent variables. The summary of the result is presented in the table below.

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T-test	P-value
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	18.311	2.121	.034	8.632	.000
	NSS	.074	.059	.083	2.051	.002
	TMS	.159	.053	.194	2.014	.003
	MFA	.091	.054	.128	2.112	.001

Table 4.2.3 T-Statistics and Probability Value from the Regression Result

Sources: SPSS 25, Version 23

Table 4.2.3 shows the coefficients of the individual variables and their probability values. Network security system (NSS) variable had regression coefficient of 0.074 with a probability value of .002. This implies that Network security system (NSS) has a positive and significant effect on fraud prevention of deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria. Transaction Monitoring System (TMS) has a regression coefficient of 0.159 with a probability value of 0.003 implying that Transaction monitoring system (TMS) has a positive and significant effect on fraud prevention of deposit money banks in Anambra State.

On a similar note, Multi-factor authentication (MFA) has a coefficient value of 0.91 and a probability value of 0.001. This shows that Multi-factor authentication (MFA) has a positive and significant effect on fraud prevention in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria.

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

4.3.1 Test of Hypothesis One

Ho: Network security system has no significant effect on fraud prevention in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria

In testing this hypothesis, the t-statistics and probability value in table 4.5 is used. Network security system has a t-statistics of 2.051 and a probability value of 0.002 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that Network security system has significant effect on fraud prevention in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria

4.3.2 Test of Hypothesis Two

Ho: Transaction monitoring system has no significant effect on fraud prevention in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria

Transaction monitoring system cost has a t-statistics of 2.014 and a probability value of 0.003 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null and accept the alternative hypothesis which state Transaction monitoring system has significant effect on performance deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria.

4.3.3 Test of Hypothesis Three

Ho: Multi-factor authentication has no significant effect on fraud prevention in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria

Multi-factor authentication has a t-statistics of 2.112 and a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that Multi-factor authentication has significant effect on fraud prevention in deposit money banks in Anambra State, Nigeria

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1: Conclusion:

This study examined the relationship between cybersecurity practices and fraud prevention in deposit money banks in Anambra State, with particular focus on network security systems, transaction monitoring systems, and multi-factor authentication. The increasing reliance on digital banking platforms has heightened exposure to cyber threats and fraudulent activities, thereby necessitating the implementation of robust cybersecurity frameworks within the banking sector. Based on the empirical findings of the study, it was established that network security systems have a positive and significant effect on fraud prevention in deposit money banks in Anambra State. This implies that the deployment of firewalls, intrusion detection systems, secure network configurations, and other protective infrastructure plays a crucial role in minimizing unauthorized access, blocking malicious attacks, and safeguarding sensitive financial information. Strong network security architecture significantly reduces the likelihood of cyber intrusions that could result in financial fraud. The study further revealed that transaction monitoring systems have a positive and significant effect on fraud prevention. This finding indicates that real-time monitoring tools, automated alerts, and data analytics mechanisms are effective in detecting suspicious transaction patterns and preventing fraudulent activities before they escalate. By identifying unusual

behaviors such as abnormal withdrawal patterns or unauthorized transfers, transaction monitoring systems enhance early detection and timely response, thereby limiting financial losses.

Lastly, the findings showed that multi-factor authentication has a positive and significant effect on fraud prevention. The use of multiple verification methods such as passwords, one-time passcodes, biometrics, or token-based authentication strengthens access control and reduces the risk of unauthorized account access. Multi-factor authentication adds an extra layer of security, making it more difficult for fraudsters to compromise customer accounts or internal banking systems. Overall, the study concludes that cybersecurity practices significantly enhance fraud prevention mechanisms in deposit money banks in Anambra State. The combined implementation of strong network security systems, efficient transaction monitoring technologies, and robust multi-factor authentication frameworks creates a comprehensive defense structure against cyber-related financial crimes. Therefore, sustained investment in advanced cybersecurity infrastructure and continuous improvement of digital security strategies are essential for safeguarding financial assets, maintaining customer trust, and ensuring the stability of the banking sector in Anambra State.

5.2: Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were made as follows:

- i. Banks should continue to invest in advanced network security infrastructure such as firewalls, intrusion detection and prevention systems, secure VPNs, and updated antivirus software. Regular network vulnerability assessments and penetration testing should be conducted to identify and fix security gaps, ensuring that unauthorized access and cyberattacks are minimized.
- ii. Banks should implement more sophisticated real-time transaction monitoring tools that use artificial intelligence and data analytics to detect unusual or suspicious activities. Continuous monitoring and automatic alert systems can enable immediate action against potentially fraudulent transactions, reducing financial losses.
- iii. Banks should require multi-factor authentication for all customer and staff access to banking systems. The use of passwords in combination with biometrics, one-time passcodes, or token-based authentication provides an additional layer of security, making it difficult for fraudsters to gain unauthorized access.

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